

		Standard Operating Procedure SOP-AVITHRAPID- CYTOTOXICITY_VIRUCIDAL CMP
Page:	1 of 6	Cytotoxicity evaluation – virucidal compounds
Version:	1	
Valid from:	06.01.2026	

	Created by	Controlled by	Approved by
Name	Anne Bull-Maurer	Marianne Maquart	Fabrizio Mammano
Email	anne.bull@univ-tours.fr	marianne.maquart@univ-tours.fr	fabrizio.mammano@inserm.fr
Date	15.12.2025	06.01.2026	06.01.2026

Index

1. GOAL AND AREA OF APPLICATION	2
2. DEFINITIONS AND ABBREVIATIONS	2
3. METHOD	2
3.1 GENERAL	2
3.2 INFORMATION FOR CONSOMABLES / CHEMICALS /EQUIPMENT	3
3.3 PROCEDURE	3
3.3.1 <i>Cell seeding (DAY 0)</i>	3
3.3.2 <i>Compounds dilutions preparation (DAY 1)</i>	4
3.3.3 <i>Compounds addition</i>	4
3.3.4 <i>Detection: CellTiter Glo assay (DAY 2 to 8 depending on the corresponding antiviral assay)</i>	4
3.3.5 <i>Data analysis and interpretation</i>	5
4. FURTHER APPLICABLE DOCUMENTS	6

		Standard Operating Procedure SOP-AVITHRAPID- CYTOTOXICITY_VIRUCIDAL CMP
Page:	2 of 6	Cytotoxicity evaluation – virucidal compounds
Version:	1	
Valid from:	06.01.2026	

1. Goal and Area of Application

Assessing cellular toxicity in the target cell line is an essential prerequisite for evaluation of the antiviral effect of a compound. This SOP applies to *in vitro* cytotoxicity testing performed on mammalian cell lines to identify non-cytotoxic concentrations for the screening of antiviral activity in cell-based assays.

2. Definitions and Abbreviations

CMPs Compounds

PPC Peptide-Porphyrin Conjugates

DMSO Dimethylsulfoxide

3. Method

3.1 General

This SOP describes the application of a commercial kit from Promega (CellTiter-Glo® Luminescent Cell Viability Assay) to assess the cytotoxicity profile of virucidal compounds through a luminescence-based cell viability assay and determine the highest dose associated with > 90% of cell viability prior to antiviral activity testing.

At least two independent toxicity determinations, in which the compounds doses are tested in duplicate, are required before selecting non-toxic concentrations.

The CellTiter-Glo® 2.0 Assay determines the number of viable cells in culture by quantifying ATP, which indicates the presence of metabolically active cells. Luminescence readout is directly proportional to the number of viable cells in culture.

NB1: the CellTiter-Glo® 2.0 Assay protocol slightly differs from the one described in the kit handbook, as detailed here below. It was developed by Ilaria Vicenti and colleagues (University of Siena, Italy).

NB2: For light-sensitive compounds, tests have to be performed IN DARK CONDITION

		Standard Operating Procedure SOP-AVITHRAPID- CYTOTOXICITY_VIRUCIDAL CMP
Page:	3 of 6	Cytotoxicity evaluation – virucidal compounds
Version:	1	
Valid from:	06.01.2026	

For example for peptide-porphyrin conjugates (PPC) to avoid potential photoactivation of porphyrins that, in presence of oxygen, generate singlet oxygen and reactive oxygen species that can lead to cell death.

3.2 Information for consommables / chemicals /equipment

Product name	Supplier	Ordering n°
DMEM High Glucose	Gibco	61965059
Fetal Bovine Serum	e.g. Gibco	e.g. 10270-106
Penicillin/Streptomycin	Gibco	15140
DMSO	Sigma	472301
CellTiter-Glo® 2.0	Promega	G9242
Sterile 96 well culture plate, flat bottom (polystyrene)	e.g. Dutscher	e.g. 353072
Opaque 96 well plate	e.g. NUNC	e.g. 436110
VeroE6 cells	Gift from Arbovirus CNR	
Huh7 LOT. 07162024	JCRB Cell Bank	#JCRB0403
PLC3 cells (a clone of PLC/PRF/5 cells)	Gift from CIIL, Center for Infection & Immunity of Lille, France	

EQUIPMENT		
Multiplate reader	e.g. BertholdTech	e.g. TriStar2S Microplate Reader
Orbital shaker	e.g. Dutscher	e.g. MS-NOR-30

3.3 Procedure

3.3.1 Cell seeding (DAY 0)

Cells are seeded in flat-bottom 96-well plates, at a defined density specific to each cell line (see below) and incubated overnight at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂ to allow proper adhesion and stabilization.

- ◆ 10,000 cells/well for VeroE6 cells
- ◆ 8,000 cells/well for Huh7 cells
- ◆ 22,000 cells/well for PLC3 differentiated cells (For differentiation protocol see SOP 'AVITHRAPID - Standard Operating Procedure - PLC3 cells differentiation before HEV infection' at <https://zenodo.org/records/20485859>)

		Standard Operating Procedure SOP-AVITHRAPID- CYTOTOXICITY_VIRUCIDAL CMP
Page:	4 of 6	Cytotoxicity evaluation – virucidal compounds
Version:	1	
Valid from:	06.01.2026	

3.3.2 Compounds dilutions preparation (DAY 1)

According to the recommendations of the compound supplier, serial 2-fold dilutions are carried out in the recommended medium (including DMSO if required for compound solubility), generally starting at 200µM or 50µM.

Then, an additional 2-fold dilution in DMEM is performed to achieve the desired final concentrations corresponding to those used to test for antiviral activity (considering that a 1/1 volume of virus will be added).

The mix are incubated 1h under agitation, mimicking the pre-incubation of viruses with CMPs in the antiviral assay.

3.3.3 Compounds addition

For Huh7 and VeroE6 cells

After removal of culture medium, cells are treated with the dilutions of CMPs in duplicate (100µL /well) for 1h before medium renewal with DMEM 2% FCS. The cells are then incubated at 5% CO₂ and 37°C for 24 to 72h before toxicity evaluation (the same duration as the incubation period required for the antiviral test).

For PLC3 cells

After removal of culture medium, cells are treated with the dilutions of CMPs in duplicate (100µL /well) and incubated overnight before medium renewal with DMEM 10% FCS. The cells are then incubated at 5% CO₂ and 37°C for 8 days with medium renewal every 2-3 days before toxicity evaluation.

For all cell lines

Six wells with untreated cells and cells exposed to a range of puromycin (six 2-fold dilutions from 4µg/mL in duplicate) are used as positive and negative control of cell viability, respectively, for the normalization of relative luminescence units from investigational compounds.

In addition, cells are exposed to dilutions of DMSO simulating the concentrations included in the dilutions of compounds (if applicable).

3.3.4 Detection: CellTiter Glo assay (DAY 2 to 8 depending on the corresponding antiviral assay)

The detection reagent should be allowed to equilibrate to room temperature before starting the procedure. If frozen, thaw the reagent at 4°C overnight. Otherwise place the bottle in a 22°C water bath. Mix gently by inverting the tube to obtain a homogeneous solution.

Note 1: proceed in the dark as soon as the reagent is added

		Standard Operating Procedure SOP-AVITHRAPID- CYTOTOXICITY_VIRUCIDAL CMP
Page:	5 of 6	Cytotoxicity evaluation – virucidal compounds
Version:	1	
Valid from:	06.01.2026	

Note 2: with the multi-channel pipettor use the same tip for all concentrations of the same compound, starting with the highest concentration (expected lowest RLU).

Upon the removal of growth medium, 60µL CellTiter-Glo reagent is added to each well
After a 10-minute gentle agitation in an orbital shaker to induce cell lysis, the lysate is homogenized by pipetting up and down 3 times
50µL from each well are transferred to an opaque 96 well plate.
The plate is incubated at room temperature for 10 minutes to stabilize the luminescent signal before recording the luminescence using a microplate luciferase reader.
Luminescence record settings: 1 second per well

3.3.5 Data analysis and interpretation

Use Excel software to import the .csv file generated by the plate reader for data processing

1. Subtract the background noise (RLU puromycin dose corresponding to 0% viability) from all measurements.
2. Calculate the average RLU of untreated and DMSO equivalent treated wells = 100% viability.
3. Calculate the % viability for each dose of the compound.

Use the Graphpad software to calculate the highest dose associated with > 90% of cell viability

1. Create XY table and copy/paste the compound doses (X) and % viability (Y)
Create one table by tested compound, one table for non treated cells and one table for puromycin control.
2. Create one graph by table (X = dose on a log scale) (Y = % viability). Indicate mean and SEM. Plot 90% viability.
3. Analyse Controls
 - Non treated cells: Check that the replicates of untreated cells show similar luciferase values, indicating reproducible measurements

Mean	5054000
Std. Deviation	370446
Std. Error of Mean	165668
Coefficient of variation	7,330%

		Standard Operating Procedure SOP-AVITHRAPID- CYTOTOXICITY_VIRUCIDAL CMP
Page:	6 of 6	Cytotoxicity evaluation – virucidal compounds
Version:	1	
Valid from:	06.01.2026	

- Control treatments: Check the Puromycin induction of toxicity and the dose to set the 0% viability of cells. Check DMSO equivalent toxicity

4. Analyse toxicity of tested compounds: use "XY analyses" tool non-linear regression (curve fit) -> Dose-response inhibition -> (Agonist) vs. response – Find ECanything -> constrain : F constant equal to 90.

4. Further applicable documents

- Manufacturer manual for CellTiter-Glo® 2.0 (Promega)
- AVITHRAPID - Standard Operating Procedure - PLC3 cells differentiation before HEV infection (<https://zenodo.org/records/20485859>)